

THE PROBLEM OF COGNITIVE GRAMMAR IN USAGE LANGUAGES

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Annotation: This article deals with the cognitive analysis of the meanings of words and phrases in English and Uzbek and their translation problems, one of the most pressing problems of modern linguistics, the study of typology of languages, predicative analysis in English and Uzbek. The specificity of its compound is described in detail.

Keywords: cognitiv-semantic analysis, word, phrase, typology, translation problems, predicative phrase.

One of the most pressing problems facing modern linguistics which is called "smallest communicative language unit" is the study of the nature of speech , general theory of language and relationship between them. Without doubt they create a theoretical system.

The study of the typology of languages not only creates a typological classification of all languages with different structures and characteristics, but also helps to determine their basic glottogonic development.

The typology of languages, which is an important and fundamental part of modern linguistics, occupies a large place in modern linguistic research because it serves to determine the nature of a phenomenon based on living, factual material.

Without any shadow of a doubt, it can be said that grammar is the main branch of linguistics that studies the grammatical structure of the language. This area of the language is a set of rules about how words change in a sentence and how they combine to form a word combination or a sentence. Grammar consists of two parts. They are: morphology and syntax. In the morphology part of the grammar, word groups and their characteristic forms are discussed, and in the syntax, it is checked whether the words are connected with each other and form a sentence or a word combination. It is known that grammar, like lexicology, studies the word, but if lexicology studies the lexical word - lexeme, grammar examines the grammatical word - the form of the word. A grammarian is a specialist in the grammar of one or more languages: a linguist. In the modern era, the term "*grammarian*" is sometimes used to refer to a grammatical purist or prescriptivist, one who is primarily concerned with "correct" usage. According to James Murphy, the role of the grammarian changed between the classical era and the Middle Ages (*Rhetoric in the Middle Ages*, 1981). Edward Sapir, H.L.

Mencken, Umberto Eco, Donatus (Roman Grammarian), Robert A. Kaster and many other scholar can be considered as great grammarians who added their contribution to the development of grammar as science. As for talking about Uzbek grammarians, U.P.Lafasov, Shuhrat Ko'chimov, Abduvahob Madvaliyev, Alijon Mamajonov, Alibek Rustamov, G'ulom Karimov and many other scholar have added great contribution to the development of the grammar and other spheres of language.

The study of the typology of all existing languages in the world, the typology of examining the similarities and differences of languages belonging to different systems and the definition of universal constants which is common to all languages give linguists the task of examining typology of specific languages and their comparative-historical grouping.

Each structure is studied not in isolation but in conjunction with other structures. We need to identify the types of predicative phrases, study their disturbance and valence, and their interaction with other types of structure.

In our study, the transformation method is used. Showing some models of predicative phrases define their function and make them appear in the text.

Since a sentence with a predicative phrase is complicated (in a predicative connection), the opposition of such a phrase is peculiar. For example, Accusatives cum infinitive in the following sentences in English:

I saw him swim, him - swim opposition can be seen and can exist only within another opposition. Exact cut (saw) - in opposition to the complex filler (him swim). Thus the complex filler enters into a complex opposition (cut - complex filler) and it has another opposition in itself.

The latter situation can be called internal opposition. Hence, in English, the secondary predicative connection occurs through the accusatives cum infinitive, which is a predicative phrase as an internal opposition. The disturbance of the complex opposition involving accusatives cum infinitive can be imagined as follows: cut - complex complement (secondary subject - secondary predicate).

The cognitive linguistics research conducted over the last decades focuses on the knowledge and ways of imagination that appear in the human mind, as well as the conceptual essence of language units. Conceptual content is conveyed through different layers of language. But according to many linguists, the most important part of conceptual information, the most important meanings from

the point of view of language are collected in grammar and, above all, in morphology. [3] That is why in this article we set ourselves the task of analyzing the idea that morphological representation should be distinguished as a method of understanding conceptual essence in language. This makes it possible to raise the issue of the role of morphology in a new way, to take a different approach to the problem of the concept of knowledge in language, and to study morphology cognitively. Addressing the issue of the cognitive nature of morphology is primarily based on the recent creation of functional (A.V. Bondarko, N.A. Kobrina, Ye.S. Kubryakova, N.A. Slyusarayeva), semiological (Yu.S. Stepanov) and functional-semiological (N.N. Boldirev) grammars. based on theories. The comprehensive development of the functional aspect in morphology allowed the creation of a thesis about its cognitiveness as early as the 80s of the 20th century. However, specific studies of morphology from a cognitive point of view were published in recent years by Y.S. Kubryakova. In determining the issues, Ye.S. Kubryakova derives from the fact that morphology is related to cognitive processes and should serve to reflect and convey their results. In this context, he says, "the functions of morphology are determined not at the level of morphemes, but in complete morphological systems representing different classes of words." According to the author, it is precisely in this case that fixation, classification and division of the world into certain categories and morphology determine the nature of the connection between words. Morphological representation corresponds to the concept of a categorical method of structuring conceptual content using morphological category and form. In this case, the morphology reflects the categorization of the most important aspects of the conceptual system and the fundamental concepts that make up a unique conceptual breadth and determine its order, thereby embodying the entire conceptual system. As an example of the implementation of morphological representation, concepts such as time, quantity, relationship can be included. [4]

By comprehending the grammatical connection of two or more interconnected words historically formed in the speech chain by a phrase, we refer to the four complex a 'of a simple spread sentence in English predicative phrases. we have a complex, a complex filler, a complex determinant, and a complex case. All of this is studied not in isolation from each other, but in an interrelationship and primarily in the possessive-cut relation, which is the first numerical predicative phrase.

The peculiarity of the predicative phrase in English is that it can form a

single part of a sentence without any reconstruction, for example:

I want you to come, but Men sizning kelishingizni istayman.

A comparative study of the means of representation of the category of predicative in different languages allows a detailed explanation of the place and interrelation of these means in each language. A lexical or lexico-grammatical category is a set of distinguishing features that help to define generalized concepts of a specific lexical relationship combined with an abstract meaning.

A morphological category is a set of affixal morphemes that represent specific forms of words that express opposite lexical or grammatical relationships that are combined into a more abstract meaning belonging to a word that performs a specific function in word combinations or sentences.

Divides all morphemes into core morphemes and affixal morphemes, and the latter (affixal morphemes) into two systems as word-modifying and word-forming morphemes, respectively, as a system of word-forming morphemes (subsystems) the sum of all morphological karegorigas that are dichotomously (i.e., two) into lexical-grammatical and functional grammatical morphemes characterizes the morphemes or morphological structure of a language.

Word-changing categories include phrases that belong to the categories of number, person, conjunction, and possession, or categories that represent the syntactic-grammatical relationship of words in a sentence. The categories of person and number consist of a set of morphologically expressing the subject-predicate relationship in the sentence, showing the opposition of concrete forms of a person and a number united in one meaning [5].

In conclusion, the category of consonant is a set of means that combines morphological expressions in a phrase or sentence with a single meaning and allows specific forms of consonant to be contrasted with each other. The category of possession, on the other hand, is the representation of a morphologically unified attributive relationship in the composition of phrases and sentences in a set of concrete possessive affixes set against each other.

References:

1. Ashurov Sh. S. Cutting typology in English and Uzbek. Nom. diss, Samarkand, 2017

2. Sweet H. A New English Grammar, Logical and Historical part. I Oxford, 2016.
3. Buranov J. Comparative grammar of English and Uzbek languages. Tashkent, 2013.
4. Daniyeva M.J. Derivational-functional and text-forming features of equestrian phrases in English. Nom.diss.avtoref., Samarkand, 2012.
5. Usmanov U. A new approach to speech analysis, SamDCHTI, Samarkand, 2014.

